

1 **Th17 cells express Aire.**

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6 Aire functions in negative selection of self-reactive TCR during lymphocyte development through activation
7 of tissue-restricted antigen, or TRA. This occurs specifically in the mTEC cells of the thymus, where Aire
8 expression is generally restricted to (1) Tolerogenic signaling through Aire in the periphery was previously
9 suggested (2). We measured total transcription in T cells subsets to discover T-cell lineage-specific gene
10 expression. We describe here biologically significant Aire expression in Th17 cells. The difference in
11 amount of Aire produced in the T cell when comparing naive T cells to Th17-type T cells was large, among
12 the largest transcriptome-wide, with lineage specific enrichment of Aire in Th17 cells. The data suggested
13 in sum that negative selection or tolerizing function occurs in the periphery, through lineage-specific
14 expression of Aire in Th17 cells (3).

15 Citations

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